

Investigating the Correlation of Inflammatory Interleukins with Biochemical and Haematological Variables Pre- and Post-Dialysis

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ABSTRACT

Kidney failure is the deterioration of kidney function and its inability to filter and excrete waste and excess water from the blood. This function is replaced by dialysis, which is considered a supportive treatment only for those suffering from severe kidney dysfunction or chronic kidney failure. The purpose of this study was to assess the predicted changes in blood parameters and their association to inflammatory interleukins before and after dialysis in patients with renal failure. Blood samples were taken before and after hemodialysis from 100 patients at Al-Ramadi Teaching Hospital. The patients ranged in age from 25 to 70 years old, with 52 men and 48 women. The statistical results of this study showed a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) in the mean values of urea, creatinine, uric acid, magnesium, phosphorus, ALP, AST, ALT, WBCs, and platelets post-dialysis compared to pre-dialysis. While there was a significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in the mean values of serum albumin, protein, sodium, calcium, ferritin, iron, RBCs, hemoglobin, interleukin-6, and interleukin-10 post-dialysis compared to pre-dialysis. Linear regression results for pre-dialysis samples showed that sodium, total protein, and AST levels were directly correlated with elevated IL-10 levels. While total protein was directly correlated with elevated IL-6 levels. Conversely, RBCs counts were inversely correlated with elevated IL-6 levels. Results in post-dialysis samples showed that creatinine, total protein, sodium, and AST levels were directly correlated with elevated IL-10 levels. While magnesium and ALT levels were directly correlated with elevated IL-6 levels. Conversely, calcium levels were inversely correlated with elevated IL-6 levels. In conclusion, the findings revealed a substantial association between inflammatory interleukins and some blood parameters pre- and post-dialysis. As a result, larger sample sizes are required in future studies to confirm the study's findings.

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KEYWORDS: Hemodialysis, Renal failure, Interleukin-6, Interleukin-10.

I. INTRODUCTION

Kidney failure is the weakening or inability of the kidneys to perform their functions normally, resulting in a reduced ability to filter and excrete waste from the blood, maintain the body's water and mineral balance, and regulate blood pressure (Romagnani et al., 2017). Despite advances in the medical and health sectors, kidney failure continues to spread among various segments of society. Kidney failure is a devastating disease that affects a wide range of tissues, organs, and vital functions (Zheng et al., 2021), in addition to its impact on the patient's psychological and social life, making it one of the leading causes of disability and death worldwide (Fletcher et al., 2022). Chronic kidney failure is a slowly progressive, irreversible deterioration of kidney function, characterized by impaired physiological efficiency and filtration capacity (Yan et al., 2021). Consequently, the body is unable to eliminate

waste and maintain a normal balance of water, sodium, and other essential chemicals. This results in increased levels of urea nitrogen and creatinine in the blood (Naber et al., 2021). Chronic kidney failure can result in numerous disorders, such as elevated levels of potassium and phosphate in the blood, as well as metabolic acidosis, which can lead to the development of numerous complications, such as vascular calcification, bone mineral disorders, and muscle atrophy (Kim, 2021).

Chronic kidney failure is a disease with a global prevalence. The World Health Organization and research centers have warned of the significant spread and significant increase in the incidence of chronic kidney failure in recent years (Francis et al., 2024). End-stage renal disease (ESRD) is a complex phenomenon characterized by kidney disease with various etiologies. Although ethnic, social, and environmental factors play a role in the development of the disease, the cause

of this failure can be attributed to several different factors, including infections, autoimmune diseases, diabetes, hypertension, endocrine disorders, cancer, and toxic chemicals (Gusev et al., 2021). The progression of chronic kidney disease to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) is a significant global public health problem, requiring dialysis and representing a major healthcare challenge (Maringhini et al., 2024).

Kidney failure is diagnosed through laboratory tests of kidney function and sometimes a kidney biopsy. The main problem in patients with chronic kidney failure is increased blood acidity, with elevated levels of urea and nitrogenous compounds, and clinical uremia (Wesson et al., 2020). Chronic kidney failure requires treatment, either by maintaining the body's internal fluid and ion balance through hemodialysis or by kidney transplantation (Fiorentino et al., 2021).

Hemodialysis is only a supportive treatment for those suffering from severe kidney dysfunction or chronic kidney failure. It does not completely cure the problem, but rather provides an artificial alternative (Canaud et al., 2021). Hemodialysis helps purify the blood of nitrogenous compounds and impurities accumulated due to kidney failure and maintains body fluid balance. Consequently, plasma biochemical parameters improve, but do not return to normal (Azar, 2013). Hemodialysis can be performed two to three times a week, and the duration of dialysis ranges from two to four hours. The duration of dialysis depends on several factors, including kidney function, the amount of waste in the body, salt levels, and body weight (Jardine et al., 2017).

However, hemodialysis is one of the best methods currently used to treat chronic kidney failure. It is essential for the patient's survival and improved functional performance. However, it has numerous negative effects on the patient, making it one of the most important fertile areas for modern research (Slinin et al., 2015). Several studies have demonstrated the potential of hemodialysis to regulate some metabolic and physiological disorders in patients that contribute to increased disease rates (Azar, 2013; Canaud et al., 2021; Jardine et al., 2017). Furthermore, certain factors, such as the type of dialysis membrane, dialysis water purity, and dietary restrictions, can increase the susceptibility of dialysis patients to inflammatory factors (Cobo et al., 2018). Inflammatory interleukins (IL-6 and IL-10) contribute to the development and progression of kidney failure. The release of these interleukins into the renal environment can cause kidney damage and lead to death in patients with kidney disease (Wei et al., 2022). Although the release of pro-inflammatory interleukins (IL-6) may promote some beneficial effects in patients with kidney failure, excessive production of these interleukins may contribute to the chronic inflammatory state in patients with kidney failure (Chen et al., 2021; Kreiner et al., 2022).

Based on the above, we examined some biochemical and hematological variables and inflammatory cytokines in patients with chronic kidney failure before and after dialysis to assess the impact of dialysis on these parameters.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study design and patients

The current study was conducted on renal failure patients who were on dialysis at the hemodialysis (HD) unit of Al-Ramadi teaching hospital in Al-Anbar province, Iraq, during the period from December 2023 to February 2025. The procedure and the purpose of the study were explained for all patients and an individually written consent letter was obtained from all patients. Totally 100 subjects participated in our study. Among them, 52 were male subjects and 48 were female subjects were their age ranging between 25 and 70 years. All the patients were in regular hemodialysis under permanent dialysis access for a period from 4 to 24 months. The patients were divided into two groups according to gender (male and female), and blood samples were taken from them before hemodialysis and after hemodialysis.

B. Samples collection and preparations

Pre- and post-hemodialysis blood samples were drawn in the midweek dialysis session to evaluate the immediate dialysis effects on different immunological, biochemical and hematological parameters. About 5 ml of venous blood was collected from these patients and placed into two tubes, the first contains an anticoagulant, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) tube for the assay of hematological parameters; and the second tube contains clotting activators (gel tube) and then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to separate serum and stored at -20°C to determine immunological and biochemical parameters.

C. Determination of Interleukins (IL-6 and IL-10)

The serum IL-6 and IL-10 levels were performed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits from R&D Systems (Minneapolis, MN, USA). Automated washing of 96-well ELISA plates was performed by a microplate washer (BioTek™ 50TS, USA), and the absorbance was measured at 450 nm using an ELISA reader (BioTek 800TS). The measurements were conducted and results were recorded following the manufacturer's instructions.

D. Determination of biochemical parameters

The levels of urea, creatinine, uric acid, albumin, total protein, magnesium (Mg), sodium (Na), phosphorus, calcium (Ca), aspartate transaminase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), ferritin, and iron in all serum specimens were measured using the Mindray BS-240 Fully Automatic Biochemistry Analyser (China).

E. Determination of hematological parameters

Blood samples were collected in EDTA tubes containing (anti-coagulant). Hematological parameters include white

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blood cells (WBCs), red blood cells (RBCs), platelets (PLT), and hemoglobin (Hb) was measured by a Sysmex XP-300(®) Hematology Analyzer (Sysmex, America, Inc.). Using Quality Control Reagent according to the manufacturing instructions to assess the validity of the assays.

F. Statistical analysis

Data were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. Pre- and post-hemodialysis levels of the different analytes were compared for the groups of male and female subjects using unpaired t-tests. All statistical analyses were generated by using GraphPad Prism (version 7.0). A confidence level of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

III. RESULTS

A. Demographic characteristics of dialysis patients

Regarding the demographic characteristics of kidney failure patients before and after dialysis, Table 1 shows the distribution of kidney failure cases by gender, with males accounting for 52% of the cases and females for 48%. The average age group at risk for the disease was 51.13 years. The average duration of dialysis for all patients was 13.8 months.

Table 1: General features of patients before and after dialysis

Variables	Pre-and post-dialysis groups
Sex	
Male n (%)	52 (52%)
Female n (%)	48 (48%)
Total n (%)	100 (100%)
Age (Years)	
Mean \pm SD	51.13 \pm 12.12
Skewness value	-0.001
Duration of dialysis (Months)	
Mean \pm SD	13.8 \pm 5.09
Skewness value	0.046

Note. Data were expressed as Mean \pm SD, frequency and percentage; Statistical analyses were performed by Chi-square followed by a t test (paired test) for multiple comparisons; ‡ t test significance (2-tailed).

B. Comparison of studied biomarkers between pre- and post-dialysis patients

In this study, we investigated whether serum kidney function levels (urea, creatinine, and uric acid) differed before and after hemodialysis. Results showed lower levels after hemodialysis compared to before hemodialysis (p -value = 0.0001), which is statistically significant. Serum albumin and total protein values were higher in the post-dialysis group compared to the pre-dialysis group (p -value = 0.0001), which is statistically significant (Table 2). The author investigated whether serum electrolyte levels (sodium, magnesium, phosphorus, and calcium) differed before and after hemodialysis. Serum sodium and calcium levels were lower

in the pre-dialysis group compared to the post-dialysis group (P value = 0.0001), which is statistically significant. Serum magnesium and phosphorus levels were higher in the pre-dialysis group compared to the post-dialysis group (p -value = 0.0001), which is statistically significant. The results showed that serum ferritin and iron levels were lower in the pre-dialysis group compared to the post-dialysis group (p -value = 0.0001), which is statistically significant. The results showed that serum liver function levels (ALP, AST and ALT) were lower in the post-dialysis group compared to the pre-dialysis group (p -value = 0.0001), which is statistically significant. The study also investigated whether blood parameters (RBCs, WBCs, Hb, and WBCs) differed before and after hemodialysis. The results showed higher values for RBCs and Hb after hemodialysis compared to before hemodialysis. While the values for WBCs and platelets after hemodialysis were lower compared to before hemodialysis (p -value = 0.0001), which is statistically significant. Regarding interleukin, the results showed higher serum levels of interleukin-6 and interleukin-10 after hemodialysis compared to before hemodialysis (p -value = 0.0001), which is statistically significant.

Table 2: Parameters studied for pre- and post-dialysis patients.

Variables	Pre-dialysis Mean \pm SD n=100	Post-dialysis Mean \pm SD n=100	p-value
Urea mg/dl	111.8 \pm 18.1	93.17 \pm 18.3	0.0001
Creatinine mg/dl	6.32 \pm 1.29	4.98 \pm 1.40	0.0001
Uric acid mg/dl	6.03 \pm 1.16	4.82 \pm 1.02	0.0001
Albumin g/dl	3.43 \pm 0.73	4.17 \pm 0.71	0.0001
Total protein g/dl	5.84 \pm 0.589	6.58 \pm 0.805	0.0001
Magnesium mg/dl	2.29 \pm 0.34	2.02 \pm 0.27	0.0001
Sodium mmol/L	139.3 \pm 6.13	143.6 \pm 7.09	0.0001
Phosphorus mg/dl	4.84 \pm 0.77	4.24 \pm 0.75	0.0001
Calcium mg/dl	8.63 \pm 1.03	9.15 \pm 0.71	0.0001
Ferritin ng/ml	280.89 \pm 98.3	291.2 \pm 97.8	0.0001
Iron μ g/dL	73.92 \pm 24.3	81.08 \pm 25.4	0.0001
ALP U/L	151.0 \pm 60.8	140.9 \pm 57.9	0.0001
AST U/L	53.1 \pm 18.2	48.5 \pm 18.3	0.0001
ALT U/L	46.3 \pm 17.5	40.9 \pm 16.8	0.0001
RBCs $\times 10^6/\mu$ L	4.49 \pm 0.55	4.65 \pm 0.55	0.0001
Hb g/dl	11.7 \pm 1.59	12.01 \pm 1.56	0.0001
WBCs $\times 10^3/\mu$ L	7.0 \pm 1.80	6.84 \pm 1.75	0.0001
PLT $\times 10^3/\mu$ L	238.8 \pm 60.9	234.2 \pm 61.7	0.0001
IL-6 Pg/ML	16.8 \pm 2.71	18.5 \pm 4.89	0.0001
IL-10 Pg/ML	9.36 \pm 4.37	10.78 \pm 5.04	0.0001

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Abbreviations: AST, aspartate transaminase; ALT, alanine transaminase; ALP; Alkaline phosphatase; RBCs, red blood cells; Hb, hemoglobin; WBCs, white blood cells; PLT, platelets; IL-6, interleukin-6; IL-10, interleukin-10. Note. Data were expressed as Mean \pm SD; Statistical analyses were performed by t test (paired test) for multiple comparisons; ‡ t test significance (2-tailed); p-value less than 5% is significant difference.

C. Association of interleukins with examined parameters in pre-dialysis patients

Table 3 illustrates the outcomes of the linear regression between IL-6 and IL-10 levels and the study parameters in the pre-dialysis group. The results indicated that total protein ($r=0.188$; $p=0.039$), sodium ($r=0.228$; $p=0.011$), and AST ($r=0.184$; $p=0.032$) were directly correlated with elevated serum IL-10 levels in the pre-dialysis group. Also, the outcomes indicated that total protein ($r=0.184$; $p=0.032$) was directly correlated with higher serum IL-6 levels in the pre-dialysis group. Conversely, the RBCs values ($r= -0.192$; $p=0.028$) were inversely correlated with elevated serum IL-6 levels in the pre-dialysis group (Table 3).

Table 3: Correlation of IL-6 and IL-10 with the parameters examined in the pre-dialysis group.

Variables	IL-6		IL-10	
	r	p-value	r	p-value
Urea	-0.089	0.190	0.087	0.194
Creatinine	0.087	0.194	0.148	0.071
Uric acid	-0.049	0.313	-0.011	0.457
Albumin	-0.045	0.330	-0.014	0.445
Total protein	0.181*	0.038	0.188*	0.039
Magnesium	0.027	0.395	-0.082	0.210
Sodium	-0.028	0.389	0.228*	0.011
Phosphorus	-0.008	0.469	-0.084	0.204
Calcium	-0.082	0.208	0.021	0.419
Ferritin	-0.043	0.334	0.052	0.303
Iron	0.033	0.373	0.025	0.403
ALP	0.063	0.267	0.087	0.196
AST	-0.028	0.390	0.184*	0.032
ALT	0.063	0.266	0.023	0.410
RBCs	-0.192*	0.028	-0.087	0.194
Hb	-0.004	0.485	-0.010	0.461
WBCs	-0.014	0.445	-0.058	0.284
PLT	0.061	0.273	-0.051	0.306
IL-6	-	-	0.041	0.342
IL-10	0.041	0.342	-	-

D. Association of interleukins with examined parameters in post-dialysis patients

Table 4 shows the results of the linear regression between IL-6 and IL-10 levels with the study parameters in the post-dialysis group. The outcomes shown that creatinine ($r=0.173$; $p=0.049$), total protein ($r=0.184$; $p=0.034$), sodium ($r=0.237$;

$p=0.009$), and AST ($r=0.183$; $p=0.034$) levels were directly correlated with raised serum IL-10 levels in the post-dialysis group. The results indicated that magnesium ($r=0.185$; $p=0.033$) and ALT ($r=0.171$; $p=0.045$) levels were directly correlated with elevated serum IL-6 levels in the post-dialysis group. Conversely, calcium levels ($r= -0.199$; $p= 0.024$) were inversely correlated with higher serum IL-6 levels in the post-dialysis group (Table 4).

Table 4: Correlation of IL-6 and IL-10 with the parameters examined in the post-dialysis group.

Variables	IL-6		IL-10	
	r	p-value	r	p-value
Urea	-0.049	0.315	0.049	0.313
Creatinine	0.098	0.166	0.173*	0.049
Uric acid	0.147	0.073	0.109	0.140
Albumin	-0.095	0.173	-0.047	0.319
Total protein	0.126	0.105	0.184*	0.034
Magnesium	0.185*	0.033	-0.081	0.212
Sodium	0.040	0.347	0.237**	0.009
Phosphorus	0.029	0.387	-0.074	0.231
Calcium	-0.199*	0.024	-0.038	0.355
Ferritin	-0.020	0.421	0.083	0.206
Iron	-0.014	0.444	-0.027	0.394
ALP	0.131	0.096	0.131	0.097
AST	0.042	0.339	0.183*	0.034
ALT	0.171*	0.045	0.054	0.296
RBCs	-0.145	0.075	-0.050	0.310
Hb	0.069	0.247	0.034	0.368
WBCs	-0.057	0.285	-0.110	0.139
PLT	-0.089	0.190	-0.065	0.261
IL-6	-	-	0.094	0.177
IL-10	0.094	0.177	-	-

IV. DISCUSSION

Some changes in hematological or biochemical parameters may reflect signs and symptoms of kidney failure in patients. Therefore, all patients' biomarkers were measured before and after dialysis. Kidney failure is a disease that causes changes in hematological parameters, such as decreased red blood cell counts and hemoglobin (Habib et al., 2017). Kidney failure can also affect biochemical parameters, such as elevated blood urea and serum creatinine (Naem et al., 2019).

In this study, different serum electrolyte levels (sodium, magnesium, phosphorus, and calcium) were found before and after dialysis. Some data suggest that dialysis can reduce the manifestations and severity of uremia in patients (Mazzaferro et al., 2021). Bamgbola (2011) he stated that anemia is one of the most important complications associated with kidney failure. Anemia can be attributed to a deficiency in the secretion or decreased effectiveness of the hormone erythropoietin, which stimulates red blood cell formation (Bamgbola, 2011).

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The causes of anemia in kidney failure patients suffering from uremia include the accumulation of nitrogenous waste, increased oxidative stress, and inflammation (Krata et al., 2018). The current results showed a significant decrease in platelet counts after dialysis compared to the pre-dialysis group. This can be attributed to a deficiency in erythropoietin and to increased blood acidity in kidney failure patients, which was found to be directly related to decreased platelet counts (Asif et al., 2018). Hemodialysis plays a major role in thrombocytopenia, as the interaction of blood with dialysis membranes and the use of heparin to prevent blood clotting in dialysis tubes lead to a decrease in platelet counts (Hakim et al., 2016).

The results showed a significant increase in the percentage of RBCs and hemoglobin after dialysis. The current results also indicated a decrease in the WBCs count after dialysis compared to the pre-dialysis group. This may be attributed to increased WBCs apoptosis due to the accumulation of nitrogenous waste (Fukushi et al., 2020). This is consistent with the findings of the current study, which states that elevated levels of inflammatory cytokines (IL-6 and IL-10) are an important factor in reducing the total WBCs count in patients with kidney failure by interfering with the process of white blood cell formation in the bone marrow. The results also showed a significant decrease in the concentration of liver enzymes ALT, AST, and ALP after dialysis. These results are consistent with a study (Sette et al., 2014), which indicated that the decrease in the concentration of ALT and AST enzymes may be attributed to the accumulation of inhibitory substances in the serum of patients with kidney failure.

In this investigate, serum IL-10 levels were lower in the pre-dialysis group compared to the post-dialysis group. IL-10 is an anti-inflammatory cytokine that plays essential roles in kidney failure (Steen et al., 2020). It is thought that increased IL-10 levels are required in kidney failing patients to reduce their severe inflammatory response. Chronic inflammation is a typical hallmark of renal failure, raising the risk of a variety of illnesses (Wei et al., 2022). IL-10 is a cytokine that regulates inflammatory processes by inhibiting the synthesis of leukocyte-derived cytokines (Saraiva et al., 2010). The higher IL-10 levels found in haemodialysis patients appear to be a counter-regulatory mechanism for controlling chronic inflammation associated with sepsis and dialysis (Alwahaibi et al., 2016).

In this investigate, serum IL-6 levels were lower in the pre-dialysis group compared to the post-dialysis group. Several previous findings have shown that dialysis patients typically have elevated serum IL-6 levels. Elevated IL-6 levels in dialysis patients may be due to several factors, including inflammation, genetics, and infection, as well as dialysis-specific factors such as dialysis solutions and membranes (Rysz et al., 2006).

Hemodialysis can stimulate the secretion of IL-6 from renal cells, which is important in the healing inflammatory processes in kidney injury (Su et al., 2017). Several studies have reported an association between serum IL-6 levels and the incidence of morbidity in hemodialysis patients (Bossola et al., 2015; Kreiner et al., 2022). In the same context, there are findings indicating that patients with kidney failure, especially those undergoing dialysis, are at risk for developing several comorbidities, such as atherosclerosis, vascular disease (Poznyak et al., 2022), and liver disease (Swift et al., 2022), which may be caused by the involvement of IL-6 due to its elevated levels in patients' serum (Kreiner et al., 2022).

Our findings of elevated serum IL-6 and IL-10 concentrations in hemodialysis patients are consistent with some previous studies. Brys et al. (2020) found that serum IL-6 concentrations increased during chronic hemodialysis in patients (Brys et al., 2020). A study reported similar findings regarding increased serum IL-10 concentrations after hemodialysis (Chen et al., 2021). A studied showed the relationship between inflammatory markers, including interleukin-6, in hemodialysis patients, and their data indicated that interleukin-6 was significantly associated with the prevalence of chronic or acute kidney failure depending on the severity of the disease (Durlacher-Betzer et al., 2018). On the other hand, our findings demonstrated that patients with renal failure who had received dialysis had greater serum levels of IL-6 and IL-10 than they had prior. Accordingly, when comparing patient samples before and after dialysis, this elevated interleukin displayed a substantial connection with certain biochemical and hematological indicators. This aligns with (Thang et al., 2020), who emphasized the significance of IL-6 in forecasting renal failure consequences and its potential as a predictor of dialysis-related conditions. Another study by (Ribeiro et al., 2022) corroborated this, indicating that increased IL-10 levels may correlate with certain biochemical markers and risk factors in dialysis patients.

V. CONCLUSION

In these findings, disparities were noted in the biomarker levels assessed in pre-dialysis samples, which were either elevated or diminished compared to post-dialysis samples. Elevated serum IL-10 levels before and after hemodialysis were directly correlated with total protein, sodium, and AST, while they were correlated with creatinine only post-dialysis. Total protein was also directly associated with elevated serum IL-6 levels before dialysis. Magnesium and ALT levels were associated with elevated IL-6 levels post-dialysis. There was an inverse correlation of elevated IL-6 values with pre-dialysis red blood cell count and post-dialysis calcium. Raised IL-10 and IL-6 amounts may predict a variety of comorbidities in kidney failure patients. However, more investigation must be done to better

understand the inflammatory pathways and associated outcomes in dialysis patients.

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